

VISUALIZATION VS. SONIFICATION TO LEVEL A TABLE

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ABSTRACT

Tiltification is a bullseye spirit level app that utilizes graphical and auditory display. In this paper I describe an experiment in which participants level a table using visualization and sonification. I found that using sonification participants can level a table significantly faster and with shorter trajectories, while the precision and the subjective workload are similar for the visualization and the sonification condition. The circumstance that the visual display is sometimes out of sight while adjusting leg lengths is certainly in favor of the sonification. This even counterbalances the fact that people have life long experience leveling furniture using a visual spirit level. Even though the experiment result may seem obvious to sonification researchers, they underline the effectiveness of sonification. Still, there is reason to believe that the results do not reflect the full potential of sonification.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2020 we developed and released *Tiltification* [1], a mobile spirit level app that communicates both tilt angles of the smartphone via visualization and our psychoacoustic sonification [2].

Several benefits of sonification have been mentioned in the literature, among them: **1.** Sonification has been described as useful in situations in which visual displays are occluded or lie outside the visual field [3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. **2.** It has been highlighted that reaction times to sound can be much shorter than to visual display [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13]. **3.** In visually complex situations, auditory displays may contribute less to attention overload than visual displays [7, 13, 14]. **4.** Sonification can increase confidence [15], lead to an increased sense of achievement [16] and can be engaging and fun [6, 7]. **5.** Sonification can increase awareness of object characteristics and processes, especially temporal patterns, that are sometimes unnoticed in visual display [3, 6, 7, 17, 18]. At the same time many researchers highlight that people are unfamiliar with the use of sonification in contrast to ubiquitous visualization [6, 19, 20].

For *Tiltification*, point 1 is particularly important, as a spirit level may be occluded when leveling furniture, e.g., when it lies on a table top while the leg length is being adjusted at the bottom of the legs. Interestingly, even though listening tests are quite common in the auditory display community [21], researchers rarely design experiments in which the advantages of sonification come into effect. As cited above, many studies argue for the use of sonification in the case of an occluded visual display. But studies that actually prove this seem rare. Instead, sonifications are often evaluated against visualizations in tasks where visualizations are already commonly applied, as in [6, 22]. However, considering the lifelong experience in the use of visualization whilst no compa-

table experience in the use of sonification exists, the superiority of visualization over sonification in such experiments seems obvious, too. One could argue that longitudinal studies allow for a fair comparison between visualization and sonification, because a long-lasting usage of sonification may counter-balance the deficit in familiarization [23, 24]. The downsides of longitudinal studies are that they are timely, costly, hard to finance, and it is difficult to motivate individuals to engage with sonification regularly over a long period of time. Alternatively, one could look for unfamiliar visualizations that are better comparable to sonification [19]. But in this case neither the potential of the sonification nor of the unfamiliar visualization become clear.

In this paper I describe an experiment in which both data presentation forms have one advantage over the other: Leveling a table. Here, visualization of tilt angles is commonly utilized and people have experience with it. This is a clear advantage of visualization over sonification, which is has never been used by many people. While leveling a table, the sonification can even be heard when the visual display is occluded, because it lies on the table top while the leg length is adjusted on the bottom of the leg. This is a clear advantage of sonification over visualization. Do these (dis-)advantages counter balance each other?

Both the sonification and the visualization can be experienced using the *Tiltification* app¹ or the open source project *Sonic-Tilt* [25].

2. METHOD

Two equal tables were installed in a lecture hall. The table tops had the shape of isocetes trapezoids, having a long side length of 70 cm parallel to a short side length of 58 cm, connected via two side lengths of 60 cm. Accordingly, the four legs of each table were arranged as an isocete trapezoid, too. A screw mechanism on the bottom made the leg lengths adjustable. I attached slices of wood with different thicknesses at the bottom of the legs to obscure the exact leg length. This way the table could not be leveled by screwing all leg levelers completely in (or out). Around 80 turns were necessary in order to screw the adjustment screw completely in. A leg with its adjustment screw and the piece of wood can be seen in a short video on <https://youtu.be/fOtIiA0TofE>. Both tables were tilted 1.2° to the right and 2.1° away from the participant. To obscure that both tables were tilted equally, I installed them with a distance of about 1.5 m to each other, with a different orientation in front of a curved wall. Figure 1 is a photo of the setup. I informed the participants that their task would be to level these tables using my smartphone — one using visualization, and the other one using sonification — and then tab the arrow button

¹Available at the respective app stores for for iOS and Android.

when they had finished the task. Then, I handed them a slim but large hardcover book as a surface and my mobile phone with the Tiltification app opened.

Figure 1: Experiment setup with the two tables with different orientations in front of a curved wall.

With this app I explained the visualization to them first. It is basically a white plus symbol in front of a gray disk. The position of the plus symbol is fixed. The behavior of the disk resembles the behavior of a bubble in a physical spirit level, i.e., the disk always drifts in the direction of the smartphone elevation. For example, when lifting the left side of the smartphone, the disk will drift to the left. This way you can level the smartphone by bringing the plus symbol to the center of the disk. When the mobile phone is almost leveled, the plus symbol turns green. When perfectly leveled, the disk also turns green. An example can be seen in Fig. 2. After the explanation, the participants could explore the visualization themselves.

Figure 2: Visualization in the Tiltification app. Here, the left hand side is elevated.

After that I explained the sonification to them. A complex tone tells them where to go. When the pitch rises, the mobile phone has to be tilted towards the right. When it falls, it has to be tilted to the left. The sonification uses a kind of Shepard tone [26] that can evoke the auditory impression of an ever rising or ever falling pitch. When the sound is rough, it has to be tilted towards you. When you hear a regular loudness fluctuation, you have to rotate it away from you. When the mobile phone is almost leveled, a background noise becomes audible. When perfectly leveled, the pitch and loudness are steady, and the sound exhibits no roughness. After the explanation, the participants could explore the sonification themselves. Together, both explanations and explorations took about 5 minutes.

Then, I informed the participants whether they would start with the visualization or the sonification, put my smartphone on

the first table and let them tap the start button as soon as they felt ready. Half of the participants started with the visualization, half of them with the sonification. For both tables the smartphone recorded its own tilt angles with a sample rate of $sr = 50$ Hz in a csv file. This way the two tilt angles over time were tracked, but not the length of the individual legs.

To compare the two data presentation types (visualization vs. sonification), I considered several measures that can be found in the sonification literature:

1. time to reach the target [27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32]
2. trajectory length [31, 33, 34]
3. precision [27, 28, 30, 32]
4. NASA-Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) [27, 28, 29, 33, 34]
5. qualitative observations in a fashion similar to studies like [29, 32, 33, 34], i.e., voluntary comments or observation of their behavior.

A priori calculation of the required sample size in a MANOVA repeated measures, within factors sufficient to detect effect sizes of $f > 0.5$, with an $\alpha = 0.05$ and a desired statistical power of $1 - \beta = 0.8$ for 2 groups and 4 measures with an assumed correlation of 0.6 yields 10 participants. This was calculated using the G-Power² freeware [35].

Consequently, I recruited $N = 10$ participants (2 female, 8 male, age ranging from 23 to 39, median = 29), mostly bachelor's and master's students in computer science with no prior knowledge of Tiltification in particular, or sonification in general.

Note that the experiment took place in a comparably ecological setting. This means the task was not abstract, but a plausible use case that people could face in real life. This may have affected the subjective workload and the performance. As there were no further restrictions, some participants have acted a little unexpectedly. The room was neither acoustically, nor visually treated. This means that both visual and auditory distractions could occur, reflections may have affected the visual display and ambient sounds may have masked the auditory display.

3. RESULTS

The quantitative experiment results are summarized in Table 1. Using the sonification the participants took 136 seconds to level the table with a precision of 0.72° . Using the visualization the participants took 234 seconds to level the table with a precision of 1.14° . MANOVA repeated measures revealed that significant differences between the two groups exist ($F(4, 15) = 3.33, p < .05$; Wilk's $\lambda = 0.529$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.33$).

Tukey post hoc test with Bonferroni correction revealed that both the time to level the table ($F(1, 18) = 8.079; p = .011$; partial $\eta^2 = 0.31$, observed power = 0.77) and the length of the trajectory ($F(1, 18) = 5.99; p = .025$; partial $\eta^2 = 0.25$, observed power = 0.64) were significantly shorter in the sonification case compared to the visualization case, the effect size was large and the observed power quite high. The precision achieved with the sonification was higher, but not significantly, and the subjective workload according to NASA-TLX was higher, but not significantly. In all cases, the standard deviation was comparably large. This indicates that the individual performances were quite diverse under each condition.

²Available at <http://gpower.hhu.de>.

Table 1: Results (ar. mean \pm standard deviation) of both data presentation methods. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are indicated by an asterisk.

	visualization	sonification
time*	234 \pm 95 sec	136 \pm 54 sec
length*	4236 \pm 2807	1995 \pm 711
precision	1.14 \pm 0.57°	0.72 \pm 0.56°
NASA-TLX	36.3 \pm 16.73	43.2 \pm 16.6

In addition to the quantitative results I’ve made some qualitative observations. First of all, a lot of jitter can be seen in the trajectory plots, i.e., the plots look very noisy. An example can be seen in Fig. 3. This is only partly due to the internal noise of the smartphone sensors. More critically, while adjusting one leg length by say 0.1°, the whole table is shaking in all directions by 1° or more. Sometimes the participant hit the table with the hip or so, which also produced unexpected patterns in the trajectories. To conclude whether their latest action has improved the leveling of the table, participants had to let the adjustment screw go for a moment. This is necessary, because either the participants had to stretch their arms or even stand up to take a look at the visualization, or they had to wait until the squeeking sound of turning the adjustment screw was over, so that they could listen to the sonification. The squeek can be heard on <https://youtu.be/fOtIiA0TofE>.

Figure 3: Exemplary trajectory of one visualization guided (blue) and one sonification guided (red) leveling run. To be distinguishable, the red trajectory is mirrored along the x - and the y -axis. Both plots exhibit jitter and huge outliers that result from lifting the table. An animation of the blue plot can be watched on <https://youtu.be/S-vgwue7DXk>.

Sometimes, the angle changed dramatically. This was because some participants sometimes lifted the whole table on either side to see/hear how the visualization/sonification changed. This may have served as a reminder of the metaphor, or as a means to see/hear better in which direction the table has to be tilted. This action dramatically increases the trajectory length, but it does not affect the duration that much. However, as can be seen in Fig. 3, it happened under both conditions. Two participants told me during the experiment that they were having troubles imagining in which direction they had to turn the screw in order to increase the leg length. This led to turns in the trajectories, because they turned the adjustment screw in the wrong direction before realizing and correcting it. Some participants did not rely on the visualization or the sonification alone. They looked at the table top from a lit-

tle distance to confirm whether the table looked horizontal or not. Some participant told me that they disliked the sonification, some complained about the shrill squeek when turning the adjustment screw.

4. DISCUSSION

In a previous experiment participants needed significantly longer to reach a target when they were guided by our psychoacoustic sonification compared to visualization [34]. This is a common result that can also be found in other studies, like [22, 27]. The reason may be that participants use visualizations readily and confidently, and make corrections on the fly. In contrast to that, they tend to be insecure in the usage of sonification, so they move slower and pause their motion often, offering some time to listen. In the present study the participants were faster, needed a shorter path and were more precise using sonification compared to visualization. One could argue that the experiment design was in favor of the sonification, because the visualization was not always visible, while the sonification was always audible. Consequently, more time was needed to look at the display every now and then. On the other hand, interpreting visualizations is part of the participants’ everyday life, while they have never even heard of the term *sonification*, nor consciously used it. In the present study, the sonifications’ advantage seems to counter balanced its disadvantage.

A debatable question is under what circumstances the comparison between visualization and sonification is fair. Immanuel Kant argued that everybody has the faculty for thinking and the faculty for concepts, but to engage, some will need more education and experience than others [36]. This has been argued to apply, for example, for music [37, chap. 2]. I think this applies to sonification usage, too. Many participants are not only inexperienced in interpreting sonification. They are not even familiar with the idea of using sonification, and not well-educated concerning sound usage. Many people have the potential to use sonification effectively, but some do it readily, whereas others would need more auditory education and experience. This is in agreement with my personal observations: In my first experiment with the psychoacoustic sonification one participant performed at chance level [38], i.e., he or she did not understand the sound metaphors after five minutes of explanation. When demonstrating the sonification interactively, at meetings and in workshops, some persons were simply unable to tell apart a rising from a falling pitch. I even remember two cases in which persons could not tell apart whether the pitch or the loudness was fluctuating. Even though I observed such inabilities only in a hand full of individuals out of some hundreds of people, it is clearly a reoccurring phenomenon. It has been suggested that around 4% of the population may suffer under dysmelodia [39], i.e. a neurally caused inability to remember and distinguish pitches well. This percentage lies in the same order of magnitude as red-green color vision deficiency, which affects 0.5% (females) to 8% (males) of people with a Northern European origin and is just slightly lower than the 10% of the population that may suffer from dyslexia [40], i.e., a reading disorder. Apart from these clinical pictures, comparably little is known about the sound perception and interaction of healthy, but uneducated and inexperienced listeners. According to the psychoacoustician Carl Stumpf, more than 75% of people who are not used to analytic listening report two consecutive tones presented at an octave interval as two tones with the same pitch but different timbres [41]. It is also well-known that non-experts exhibit less consistent audio

quality ratings and that experts are more reliable, quick and sensitive [42, p. 4][43]. These and other effects may heavily affect the apparent efficacy of sonifications in experiments, leading to a severe underestimation of the true potential that a sonification would have in a society with a higher awareness of and a better education in hearing. On the other hand, I have met some people that were extraordinary resolute and readily good at interacting with the psychoacoustic sonification, and instantly imagined potential use cases. According to Kant, everybody may have the faculty for this. If so, should we really look at the average performance of naive participants to evaluate sonifications? Or should we focus more on the best performing individuals for a better estimation of the true potential of a sonification. In my opinion, evaluating sonification in interactive experiments today is a bit like an evaluation of how fast a person could typewrite in the 1870s just after the first typewriters became available. The results do not reflect the full potential that the new technology could have in a society with more education in and experience with typewriting. Of course, such a society was speculative in the 1870s, but one hundred years later it became reality. People had grown up with typewriters and used them in their everyday lives, e.g., in school, college, at work and privately. And the majority certainly typed faster than the people a hundred years earlier. The society had adopted to the technology, so its benefits could unfold. This may or may not happen with sonification, too. But it certainly will not happen if studies fail at making the potential of the sonification imaginable to the readers. A carefully chosen experiment design can at least highlight some of its benefits.

Even though the result seems obvious to sonification researchers, I think experiments like the one presented in this manuscript underline the benefit of sonification and allow speculations about the true potential of sonification.

Finally, note that the results also indicate that the spirit level sonification may make the spirit level accessible to blind and visually impaired people, without a significant loss in precision, rise in completion time or rise in subjective workload compared to sighted people.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper I presented an experiment in which 10 participants had to level one table using visualization and another one using sonification as a means to display their tilt angles. Sonification enabled them to level the table significantly faster and with shorter trajectories, while both the precision and the subjective workload were not significantly different compared to visualization.

A natural strength of visualization is that people have life long, daily experience using it consciously, which does not apply to sonification. A natural strength of sonification is that sound deflects around obstacles, so users can even hear the sonification from occluded devices, which does not apply to visualization. In this particular experiment the advantage of sonification over visualization counter balanced its disadvantage, when comparing the average performance. I argue that this result still underestimates the true potential of the psychoacoustic sonification, as the performance of the participants is the performance of people with little education and experience in sonification compared to visualization. Experiments with better educated and more experienced sonification users could reflect its true potential much better. However, for the time being the experiment results show that sonification can already be superior to visualization when the task is to

level a table.

6. REFERENCES

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